

USG (4-14%). Labeled N utilization was 42% with PU, 30% in grain and 12% in straw (see figure). Only 8% of the labeled N applied as USG was utilized (6% in grain and 2% in straw).

Isotopic composition of rice grain and straw showed that 40% grain N and 35%

straw N were derived from PU; 13% grain N and 12% straw N were derived from USG.

Soil analysis at harvest showed that 26% of the labeled N from PU and 13% from USG were retained in the soil. Total recovery of labeled N in crop and

soil was 68% for PU, 21% for USG; 32% PU N and 79% USG N was not accounted for in the N balance. The large deficit of N from USG was attributed to its rapid movement and leaching from concentrated zones at placement sites. □

Sesbania rostrata — a lower-cost source of N for rice

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We studied the effect of stem-root nodulating *S. rostrata* and sunn hemp *Crotalaria jancea* on transplanted irrigated rice Mandya Vijaya (145-150 d duration) during summer 1988.

Soil of the experimental site was red sandy loam (Alfisols), pH 6.3, medium N (1.1% organic matter), 10.6 kg available Olsen's P/ha, and 151 kg available K/ha. N content was 4.1% in *S. rostrata* and 3.2% in sunn hemp.

At the same level of applied N, yield increased significantly (15%) over farmers' practice (treatment 1), with 30% N supplied through *S. rostrata* (treatment 2) (see table). The cost

involved in supplying N through *S. rostrata* was \$12, compared to urea cost of \$15. Use of *S. rostrata* increased net profit by \$125/ha. *S. rostrata* (treatment 4) could substitute for fertilizer N up to 70 kg N/ha (treatment 6) without significant yield reduction.

S. rostrata was significantly superior to sunn hemp (treatment 5). Uptake of N was better with *S. rostrata*. □

Effect of *S. rostrata* on rice yield. ^a Karnataka, India.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)	Total uptake of N in grain + straw (kg/ha)
1. 100 kg N/ha as urea in 3 splits: 1/2 at planting + 1/4 at tillering + 1/4 panicle initiation (farmers' practice)	4.5	92
2. 30 kg N/ha through <i>S. rostrata</i> + 70 kg N/ha as urea in 2 splits: 1/2 at planting + 1/2 at tillering	5.2	110
3. 30 kg N/ha through sunn hemp <i>C. jancea</i> + 70 kg N/ha in 2 splits: 1/2 at planting + 1/2 at tillering	4.8	97
4. <i>S. rostrata</i> to supply 70 kg N/ha	3.4	76
5. Sunn hemp to supply 70 kg N/ha	3.0	68
6. 70 kg N/ha as urea in 2 splits: 1/2 at planting + 1/2 at tillering	3.2	71
7. Control (no N)	2.4	47
LSD (0.05)	0.3	6
CV (%)	10.8	5.3

^aAll treatments received 22 kg P and 41 kg K/ha.

Nitrogen-use efficiency with hand- and machine-applied N fertilizers in wetland rice soils

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Prilled urea (PU) farmer's split (F), researcher's split (R), modified split (M), applicator placed (AP); and urea

supergranules (USG) hand placed (H) and AP were compared in a field experiment during the 1986 dry season. BR3 was the test variety.

Soil was clay loam (Paleudults) with pH 6.5, 1.05% organic matter, CEC 24 meq/100 g, 0.07% total N, and incubated 57 ppm NH₄⁺-N (incubated at 30 °C for 1 wk). Two rates of N (58 and 87 kg/ha) and 1 control treatment were used. P at 17.6 kg/ha, K at 33.2 kg/ha, and S at 20 kg/ha were applied

Effect of N fertilizer application method on yield of BR3 and agronomic efficiency of N, 1986 dry season, BRRI, Joydebpur, Bangladesh. ^a

Treatment ^a	Plant height (cm)	Tillers (no./m ²)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Agronomic efficiency (kg grain/kg N)
Control	86	210 e	195 c	3.6 c	-
58 PU (F)	93	243 d	231 b	4.9 ab	23
58 PU (R)	91	286 bc	269 ab	4.6 b	18
58 PU (M)	89	267 bcd	256 ab	4.8 ab	20
58 PU (AP)	94	309 a	295 a	5.3 a	30
58 USG (H)	93	299 a	283 a	5.3 ab	29
58 USG (AP)	94	285 abc	269 ab	5.4 a	31
87 PU (F)	91	272 abcd	263 ab	5.2 ab	19
87 PU (R)	92	260 cd	242 b	5.0 ab	16
87 PU (M)	94	281 abcd	268 ab	4.9 ab	15
87 USG (H)	94	293 ab	271 ab	5.4 a	20
CV (%)	4	2	2	8	

^a Within a column, means followed by a common letter do not vary significantly at the 5% level of DMRT. ^b F = 1/3 basal + 1/3 30 d after transplanting (DT) + 1/3 at panicle initiation (PI), R = 2/3 basal + 1/3 at PI, M = 1/3 15 DT + 30 DT + 1/3 at PI, AP = applicator-placed at 10-12 cm depth, H = hand-placed at about 10-12 cm depth.

during final land preparation.

Regardless of method, 58 kg N/ha significantly improved panicles/m² and yield (see table). USG gave a grain yield advantage of 0.5 t/ha over PU. Differences among F, R, and M were

minimal.

Machine application increased yield 0.4-0.7 t/ha over broadcast split with PU at 58 kg N/ha. There was no difference between hand and machine

application methods with USG.

Placement of N fertilizer in the reduced zone as PU by machine or as USG by hand or machine gave higher agronomic efficiency. □

Effect of Zn and Cu on growth and nutrition of rice

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We studied the effect of soil application of Zn and Cu on dry matter yield and tissue concentration of Zn, Cu, Fe, Mn, and P in rice grown under submerged soil in a pot experiment in the greenhouse.

Soil was silty clay loam containing 20 ppm Olsen's P and DTPA extractable 0.64 ppm Zn, 0.46 ppm Cu, 11.6 ppm Fe, and 22.5 ppm Mn. Each pot contained 4.56 kg soil.

Basal nutrient application was 100 ppm N as urea, 26 ppm P as diammonium phosphate, and 25 ppm K as potassium chloride. Soil treatments were 0, 5, 10 and 20 ppm Zn and 0, 1, 2, and 5 ppm Cu as sulfates in a factorial combination with 2 replications.

Dry matter yield (g/pot)

Effect of Zn and Cu on dry matter yield of rice.

Effect of Zn and Cu on nutrient concentration in rice. ^a

Nutrient levels (ppm)	Nutrient concentration									
	µg/g tissue				mg/g tissue					
	Zn		Cu		Fe		Mn		P	
	S	R	S	R	S	R	S	R	S	R
Zn 0	50.8	59.0	27.0	31.6	0.40	4.66	0.20	0.57	1.12	1.30
Zn 5	56.3	60.8	25.4	30.7	0.40	4.40	0.20	0.66	1.02	1.15
Zn 10	69.3	67.6	24.8	28.1	0.40	4.06	0.20	0.75	1.00	1.26
Zn 20	73.7	72.8	20.5	24.1	0.34	3.44	0.19	0.64	0.90	1.26
Cu 0	73.4	73.6	21.5	25.1	0.40	4.49	0.20	0.55	1.11	1.16
Cu 1	62.6	67.6	21.9	29.7	0.38	3.55	0.19	0.67	1.00	1.00
Cu 2	62.6	60.5	26.6	28.6	0.40	4.47	0.20	0.62	0.99	1.28
Cu 5	51.6	58.6	27.8	31.1	0.36	4.02	0.20	0.78	0.95	1.53
LSD (0.05)	5.4	1.8	1.9	1.9	0.02	0.25	0.01	0.06	0.02	0.04

^a S = shoots, R = roots.

Five 20-d-old IR8 seedlings were transplanted in each of 32 pots, thinned to 3 plants/pot, and grown for 72 d. Additional 20 ppm N as urea was applied 40 d after transplanting.

Highest increase in dry matter yield was from 10 ppm Zn + 2 ppm Cu (see figure). Application of 5 ppm Zn + 1 or 2 ppm Cu also increased yield. The highest rates of Zn (20 ppm) + Cu (5 ppm) failed to increase dry matter yield.

Zn in roots and shoots increased with Zn application but decreased with Cu

application (see table). Cu in roots and shoots increased with Cu application but decreased with Zn application of 10 ppm or more. Fe in roots decreased at all Zn levels and at 1 and 5 ppm Cu. Fe in shoots decreased with 20 ppm Zn and 1 and 5 ppm Cu. Mn in roots increased with Zn and Cu; in shoots, it decreased with 20 ppm Zn and 1 ppm Cu. P in shoots decreased with Zn and Cu. In roots, it decreased at all Zn levels and at 1 ppm Cu. Application of 2 and 5 ppm Cu increased P in roots. □

Biofertilizer production of stem-cut planted and seeded *Sesbania rostrata*

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Although *S. rostrata* is a promising green manure species for lowland rice farming systems, production of seed and scarification may be a problem for

farmers. Vegetative propagation appears attractive because nodulation sites constitute primordia of adventive roots able to grow under waterlogged conditions.

We compared biofertilizer production by vegetative propagation through stem cuttings (30 and 20 cm) and broadcast seeding, at 3 plant densities.

The experiment May-June 1988 at IRRI farm was laid out in a randomized split-plot design with four replications.